

PEDAGOGICAL MODEL OF INTERACTION OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION AND FAMILY BASED ON INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

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Abstract. *This article describes the organization of interaction between preschool education organizations and families based on innovative approaches. Family and preschool educational organization are two educational phenomena, each of which in its own way gives the child social experience, but only in harmony with each other do they create optimal conditions for a little person to enter the big world. It is possible to compensate and soften each other only in harmonious relations between the preschool educational organization and the family. When parents become direct creators of the interesting lives of their children, interest and confidence arise both in preschool and at home, which allows them to learn about other families' cultural traditions and different approaches to education.*

Keywords: *diagnostic tools, personality development, pedagogical activity, reflection, reflective activity, pedagogical reflection.*

Today, many preschool education organizations in cities and villages are focused on finding forms and methods of work that take into account the current needs of parents and serve to form an active position of parents. Modern conditions of activity of preschool educational organizations place interaction with the family in one of the leading places.

Families are in a state of acute crisis:

- Social;
- economic;
- political.

The organization of preschool education, together with parents, is responsible for the development of the child's personality. How can a family participate in the life of a preschool? How can we make the process enjoyable for children, teachers, and parents?

The practice of organizing preschool education has shown that parents are interested in what happened to the child during the day, what achievements or difficulties this day brought him; and educators receive information from parents about long-term goals, hopes and aspirations for the future of their child and family, but insufficient interaction between teachers and parents can be observed as follows:

pedagogical and psychological illiteracy of parents, lack of existing knowledge.

lack of interest in traditional forms of communication (in the middle group it decreases): meetings, consultations, conversations.

parents do not pay due attention to the child's personality and mental development children are highly intelligent and organized

According to the results of a survey conducted by psychologists and teachers of preschool educational organizations, it became clear that traditional work has partially ended. Parents suggested more interesting, new and acceptable forms of work in organizing preschool education.

As part of our research, we divided the work into three areas:

- *parent-child relationships*
- *cooperation between teachers and parents.*
- *interaction between child and teacher.*

During the work, the following studies were carried out:

Self-perception of a preschool child in the family and organization of preschool education.

- *Child-parent relationships*
- *Family learning style*
- *Teacher's communication style with parents.*

Together with a psychologist-educator, a set of diagnostic tools was developed:

- 1. Methods for diagnosing child-parent relationships.*
- 2. Methods for diagnosing interaction between educators and parents.*
- 3. Methods for diagnosing interaction between teachers and children.*

The style of interaction between the teacher and children was studied by a psychologist-educator. The result showed that the teacher focuses on the real child and takes him for granted, trying to build his educational impact in accordance with his individual characteristics. Prefers to follow a democratic style of communication.

Family and preschool educational organization are two educational phenomena, each of which in its own way gives the child social experience, but only in harmony with each other do they create optimal conditions for a little person to enter the big world. It is possible to compensate and soften each other only in harmonious relations between the preschool educational organization and the family. When parents become direct creators of the interesting lives of their children, interest and confidence arise both in preschool and at home, which allows them to learn about other families' cultural traditions and different approaches to education. This will help to avoid problems in the relationship between parents and children in the future and quickly find the right way out of a difficult situation.

It is in the family that the child receives the basic knowledge about the world around him. Family is a certain moral and psychological climate; This is a school of human relations for a child. With close people in the family, the child develops feelings of love, friendship, duty, responsibility, justice... Upbringing in the family is, first of all, characterized by communication, a certain tone, a certain "connection", the internal state of the child and its direct influence on him. Communication solves the problem of improving relationships with the child, changing his condition and behavior. However, there are certain difficulties, contradictions and shortcomings of educational influence in the family.

The teacher's merit in improving preschool education and family cooperation is incomparable. In interaction with the family, it is necessary to take into account three areas: personal development, pedagogical activity, reflection.

The training of teaching staff in preschool educational organizations is pedagogical thinking (gnostic, i.e. mental abilities - the ability to distinguish scientific information, the correct application of scientific knowledge in practical activities, the competent solution of pedagogical problems); setting a pedagogical goal (organizational skills - the ability to create optimal conditions for learning

and repetition, selecting the necessary forms of training, correct distribution of time, providing the educational process with the necessary equipment

organizing your work, planning and holding any events (matinees, literary evenings, etc.);

- pedagogical orientation (communication skills: the ability to present information in a general form for a certain category of students, adjust the methods and means of presenting information depending on the situation, the ability to convince someone, “teacher-teacher”, “teacher-parent”, “teacher-competent construction of professional communication at the manager”, “teacher-child” levels);

- creation of a positive psychological microclimate in the children’s team, etc.).

Professional training of teaching staff of preschool educational organizations:

- pedagogical tact (the ability to design intellectual work: remove simple standards and methods of decision-making and look for new, wonderful ones; be able to see above this and what is known to oneself; highlighting the main dependencies of common problems;

- be able to clearly see several different ways of making decisions and choose the most effective one;

- awareness and presence of a problem in which all issues are resolved;

- ideological productivity;

- designing the educational process taking into account the individual development of the child, innovative curriculum, program, own activities, etc.).

In didactic processes in preschool educational organizations, reflection plays an important role, ensuring the development and social adaptation of the child.

“Reflective activity is the formation of conclusions based on the child’s understanding and independent analysis of his concepts and actions.”

So, in didactic processes in preschool educational organizations, the stage of reflection in ensuring the child’s development and social adaptation is reflected in the activities of the teacher and the activities of the child.

Pedagogical reflection (reflexive sensitivity of skills) includes 3 types:

- feeling of the object;

- the teacher’s special sensitivity to how reality resonates with children, the extent to which children’s interests and needs are manifested in it, “to adapt them to the requirements of the pedagogical system”;

- a sense of norm and tact is manifested in special sensitivity to the extent to which changes occur in the child’s personality and activity under the influence of various pedagogical means, what changes generally occur, positive or negative, according to what signs that we can talk about them; the sense of responsibility is determined by the teacher’s sensitivity to the shortcomings of personal activity, criticality and responsibility for the educational process).

The above is important for ensuring the development of the child in didactic processes in preschool educational organizations and indicates that the child and the teacher are subjects of the educational process.

The uniqueness of pedagogical work lies in the impossibility of complete programming, although there is some consistency in the methods and skills used. The application of such standardized methods in constantly changing non-standard situations requires constant modernization and adjustment. As a source of individual creative action, the hidden and open

contradiction between the general actions noted and known in pedagogical activity and the need to find new solutions to solve emerging practical issues is considered.

The idea of cooperative relations between a preschool educational organization and a family is reflected in a number of legal documents. Today this problem is discussed by teachers, scientific researchers, psychologists, parents, and sociologists. Practice and scientific research show that parents experience difficulties in raising children for a number of reasons.

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